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Re-Value Impact Model (intermediate version)

Re-Value Deliverable D1.3

Report information

Deliverable: D1.3: Re-Value Impact Model (intermediate version)

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Authors: Marjan Khaleghi, Annemie Wyckmans, Han Vandevyvere

Executive Summary and Chapter 1: Annemie Wyckmans (NTNU)

Chapters 2 and 3: Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU), section 3.1: Annemie Wyckmans (NTNU)

Chapter 4: Han Vandevyvere (VITO), Annemie Wyckmans (NTNU), and Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU)

Chapter 5: Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU) and Annemie Wyckmans (NTNU)

All charts: Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU)

Additional report contributors: Andreas Amundsen (Ålesund Municipality), Lies Debbaut (Bruges Municipality), Koen Timmerman (Bruges Municipality), Fay Vanclooster (Bruges Municipality), Irina Elena Crista (Constanța municipality), Alberto Della Valle (Rimini Municipality), Alessandra Pesaresi (Rimini Municipality), Candida Catani (Rimini Municipality), Konstantina Douka (UNIBO), Zoya Stoyanova (Burgas Municipality), Gergana Ivanova (Burgas Municipality), Yana Yancheva (District Information Points, Burgas), Teodora Bojilcheva (District Information Points, Burgas), Stanimira Gospodinova (District Information Points, Burgas), Katherine Weir (NTNU), Deborah Navarra (NTNU), Francesco Camilli (NTNU), Anne Sunniva Bratsberg Nygren (NTNU), Shreejana Poudyal (NTNU), and all the city stakeholders who participated in the workshops.

Task contributors: NTNU Norway, Municipality of Ålesund, City of Bruges (Stad Brugge), Burgas Municipality, Municipality of Rimini, Cascais Ambiente, ADI-ZMC, İzmir Metropolitan Municipality, Písek municipality, City of Rijeka, ICLEI Europe, VITO, Alma Mater Studiorum-Università di Bologna, LNEG, IZTECH, University of Nova Gorica, IFLA Europe, Sørsida, Augment City, SU "St. Kliment Ohridski", JA Europe, Municipality of Constanța, Ecoten, Teatret Vårt, Sladovna Písek

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Executive Summary

How can waterfront cities achieve their climate goals while improving the quality of urban life? In Re-Value, 9 waterfront cities are exploring this challenge in pilot areas and long-term territorial transformation plans. Ålesund, Bruges, Burgas, and Rimini will lead the way, while Cascais, Constanta, Izmir, Písek, and Rijeka will learn from them and develop their own strategies.

To explore potential co-benefits and conflicts of interests in the cities' journey to climate neutrality in the Waterfront Pilots, we organised Impact Model workshops in each city. The workshops were hosted by the municipality, with participation by local partners and stakeholders. For background information and context on the development of the Impact Model, we kindly refer the reader to Deliverable 1.1¹.

As a tool for these workshops we gamified the NEB Impact Model into a deck of cards for the stakeholders to play with. The cards help the participants to explore the qualities of the waterfront pilots, in terms of environment, healthy living, social and cultural characteristics, economic conditions, and governance processes. We investigate existing qualities and how to strengthen these, identify missing ones, and design pathways to fill the gaps. The workshops' results are integrated in the cities' Waterfront Pilot Roadmaps.

This report (Deliverable 1.3) provides an overview of the first six Impact Model workshops held in Spring 2024 in Ålesund, Bruges, Rijeka, Rimini, Burgas, and Constanța. It details how the Impact Model has been utilized to assist these cities in developing their roadmaps through the workshops. The next three workshops, currently in progress, are taking place in Autumn 2024 in İzmir, Cascais, and Písek, and their outcomes will be covered in Deliverable 1.5 in 2026, with intermediate summaries shared on the Re-Value website.

In Phase 2 of the Re-Value project (July 2023 - June 2024), we have organised Impact Model workshops in the four Lead Cities and two Replication Cities to identify important local qualities in their Waterfront Pilots, together with the local partners, inhabitants and professionals. This includes qualities that already exist on site and should be strengthened, as well as qualities that may be generated through the Re-Value measures. In addition, we have identified potential local co-benefits between climate action and urban quality, across sectors.

In this work, the Impact Model serves as a tool for navigating the diverse needs, preferences, and concerns of different stakeholders. It aims to manage potential conflicts of interest and highlight the mutual benefits of collaborative actions across various sectors. By doing so, it seeks to increase the willingness of various stakeholders to support such initiatives. Additionally, the Impact Model helps the Re-Value cities pinpoint areas that may have been overlooked and address gaps in their current systems for measuring progress. It also strengthens their ability to implement integrated urban planning and design strategies that consider not only technical and environmental factors but also social, cultural, governance, quality of life, and economic aspects.

These Impact Model workshops are described in Chapter 2 (conceptualisation) and Chapter 3 (implementation). In Chapter 4, we present some general reflections across the workshops, on how the

¹D1.1 Re-Value Impact Model initial version, November 2023.

<https://re-value-cities.eu/documents/re-value-impact-model-initial-version>

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Impact Model itself, as well as its implementation in the cities, can be further fine-tuned. In Chapter 5, we identify next steps, including Impact Model workshops in the remaining three Replication Cities. The insights gained from the Impact Model workshops are intended to support cities in their practical efforts while integrating them into the Innovation Cycles. This iterative approach strengthens both frameworks, allowing them to evolve through mutual feedback drawn from real-world experiments and practices. The updated Impact Model will function as both a tool for facilitating stakeholder discussions and a means of advancing city initiatives.

Figure: Snapshots of the Impact Model workshops in action

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1 What is this report about?

Re-Value's Impact Model, initially outlined in D1.1² and put to the test in D1.3, will assist our cities and their local partners and stakeholders in crafting and executing well-rounded integrated urban planning and design strategies for areas undergoing urban transformation. These strategies will prioritise aspects such as quality, inclusivity, and other non-monetary advantages alongside financial and greenhouse gas emission considerations. Through collaborative efforts to refine the Impact Model, we aim to uncover both the shared benefits and potential conflicts arising from these various perspectives within and across our cities.

Before the current series of city Impact Model workshops, we initially introduced the concept through an online Community of Practice Round (organised by WP6, in February 2024). We then tested the gamified methods with all Re-Value cities and partners during the consortium meeting and city visit in Ålesund, held in March 2024.

In March - June 2024, NTNU organised Impact Model workshops on-site together with each of the Leading Cities (Ålesund, Bruges, Burgas, Rimini) as well as two of the Replication Cities (Rijeka and Constanța). The remaining three Replication Cities (Cascais, İzmir and Písek) will host their Impact Model workshops in Autumn 2024.

Each Impact Model workshop, hosted in a Re-Value city, brought together municipal authorities, local partners, and stakeholders to collaboratively use the simplified, gamified version of the Impact Model known as the Impact Model Dominoes.

The workshop begins with local stakeholders identifying strengths and gaps in their waterfront pilot neighborhoods, discussing ways to enhance the area, and addressing potential conflicts. Participants then outline strategies for implementation, including required actions, data, partnerships, and investments. In the reflection session after the workshop, municipal experts and project partners review these findings to refine the city's roadmap for waterfront transformation, focusing on practical projects that showcase sustainable urban development.

Additionally, in certain workshops, members from WP1 Innovation Cycles (story-building, scenario-building, and investment and partnership building) and WP7 Monitoring and Documenting Impact took part to understand how the Impact Model workshop works and how it could contribute to their respective work streams.

The Impact Model workshops helped develop a comprehensive understanding of complex urban transformation issues by illustrating connections across project aspects, breaking disciplinary boundaries, and improving city decision-making through effective communication among departments and stakeholders.

² D1.1: Re-Value Impact Model (initial version)

<https://re-value-cities.eu/sites/default/files/media/images/documents/D1.1%20Re-Value%20Impact%20Model%20%28Initial%20Version%29.pdf>

2 Impact Model workshops: concept development

2.1 How did we develop the Impact Model workshop format?

NTNU created a gamified workshop format around the Impact Model, in order to make it easier for local stakeholders to test it in their own neighbourhoods. In the section below, we explain how the workshops are held. During the Ålesund consortium meeting, this format was tested before implementing it in the Re-Value cities with local stakeholders.

2.2 Essential information and rules for the participants

2.2.1 The Impact Model Dominoes

The Impact Model or the Impact Framework is a tool to talk, to map, to inform, and to support better decision-making based on the whole-system approach. It tries to bring attention to the fact that the interventions in the cities' transformation areas should not be solely focused on environmental/technical performances. Quality of life, social/cultural and economic performances, and governance must all be considered.

Figure: Different layers of the Impact Model

The Impact Model might be too complicated to apply. Hence, we decided to not expose it to the users all at once, especially when non-experts are expected to use it. By breaking it down into smaller knowledge packages and introducing these in different stages of the workshop, the model becomes more straightforward and accessible for everyone, getting a chance to comprehend it step by step.

For this reason, a gamified approach was devised as an entry point to the Impact Model. We call it the "Impact Model Dominoes" since it uses similar principles as the Dominoes game. The game is a tool to operationalise the principles of the Impact Model (its holistic essence and to see how every topic is connected to the others one way or another). The cards in the picture are made with the topics on the outer ring of the Impact Model.

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Figure: Impact model dominoes (created with the topics in the outer layer of the Impact Model)

We have been applying the tool with a variety of stakeholders coming from different backgrounds and levels of expertise to let them brainstorm, discuss and empower them to shape the future of the transformation project. In this sense, the tool bridges the gap between experts and non-experts in discussing hard and multi-layered, and scary, topics. We may be playing a game but it is the most serious one as it connects many people together over a shared common and the future of their living.

The gamified tool was then integrated in a workshop module, the agenda and details of which can be found in the following. The timings could slightly vary and be modified depending on the number of participants and the needs of the city.

2.2.2 Scope of an Impact Model workshop

With these city-stakeholder workshops, we aim to operationalise and qualify the Impact Model originally developed in CrAft, for Re-Value cities by iterating the process on different cases (an area, a building, tools, and so forth). An innovative gamified Impact Model workshop module, based on the idea of the Impact Model Dominoes was devised before the Consortium Meeting in Ålesund and the series of Impact Model workshops in Re-Value cities were planned to be held by June 2024. Each workshop includes a 3-4-hour session with stakeholders and a 2-4-hour follow-up session with the Re-Value cities' core group (either in a 24-hour or a lunch-to-lunch format). At least three people from NTNU joined the workshops in person for leading and facilitation.

Figure: Impact Model Dominoes played in Rimini with Italian cards/May 2024

The Impact Model workshop for stakeholders (first session) is designed to hold **group discussions in small groups of 4-10 people from various backgrounds** (people are usually pre-assigned to tables to guarantee a maximum of diversity). This group layout has been very effective in hearing different perspectives and sharing freely in a respectful manner, especially among various Re-Value cities' internal and external stakeholders who may not interact in such a way on a regular basis.

During the first session of the workshop (with stakeholders), participants, in groups, start with identifying "current" and "future" impacts of the pilot project with the Domino cards, and then play the Dominoes to find the connections between the selected cards/topics. The half blue (co-benefits) and half red (conflicts) circles are placed at the edge of the cards for this reason. Next, they decide on an impact pathway and try to discuss all the details that make it actionable (list of tasks, resources, data, stakeholders, KPIs, and so on).

During the second session with the core-group, NTNU and Re-Value cities synthesise the findings and discuss the integration of the results in the cities' roadmaps. The iteration of workshops in different cities has helped us improve it every time and also identify barriers and success points in diverse contexts.

2.2.3 Detailed agenda of an Impact Model workshop

2.2.3.1 General overview

- Duration: Approximately 3.5 hours
- Teams: 3-8 participants with one facilitator per group
- Objective: Evaluate and rethink a project to amplify its impact on the city and its citizens using the Impact Model as a tool.

2.2.3.2 Workshop Agenda

Introduction

- Welcome & Sense-making (10 min)
- Participants' self-introduction (15 min)
- Agenda overview (5 min)
- Short presentation of the project site (15 min)

PART ONE: Identifying the impacts (65 min)

- Current & potential impacts, a starter point for the next exercise (20 min)
- Synergies and conflicts (25 min)
- Inter-group reflection & feedback collection (15+5 min)

Coffee break (15 min)

PART TWO: Creating an actionable impact pathway (65 min)

- Decide on an impact pathway and pinpoint the actions (20 min)
- Creating an agenda: discuss timeframe, stakeholders, data, finance, and regulation (25 min)
- Inter-group reflection & feedback collection (15+5 min)

Closing (10 min)

2.2.3.3 PART ONE: Identifying the impacts (65 min)

Current & potential impacts, starter for the next exercise (20 min)

Materials:

- City map, 1 deck of 46 Impact model Domino cards and extra blank cards, markers.

Activity:

After the facilitator randomly deals all the cards to you (the participants),

- Familiarise yourself with your cards (description at the back of each card) and the city map. (5 min)
- Take turns and start with placing any cards on the map where there is already an existing impact under that topic written on the card (you may briefly explain your reasons). (5 min)
- Repeat the previous step, this time for possible future impacts. (5 min)
- The 46 cards are just a list of suggestions. Create new cards with the blank extras. (2.5 min)
- Based on the discussions, make a new card with a lead topic for your group. (2.5 min)

Figure: Current & potential impacts; İzmir Impact Model workshop with Turkish Domino cards/Nov. 2024

Impact Model Dominoes: finding synergies and conflicts (25 min)

Materials:

- City map, the cards selected to be placed on the map in the previous section, markers.

Activity:

After the facilitator collects the cards on the map and randomly distributes them again to you (the participants) and places the lead topic card on the map,

- Take turns and if you find a positive link/synergy between one of your cards and the lead topic card, connect them with the blue half circles exactly like you connect pieces in Dominoes.
- If you identify a negative link or a conflict of interest, connect them with the red half-circles
- Discuss the implications of these connections each time you play and continue finding more links. (25 min)
- The game ends when time runs out.
- You may bring back some of the unplayed cards from the previous round into play if you find them relevant in this part.
- Be creative, you may interpret the game rules as you see fit and even invent new rules!

Inter-group reflection & feedback collection (15+5 min)

- Briefly share your findings with other groups (each group gets 3-5 min)
- Answer a few questions on the screen (5 min)

Figure: Synergies and conflicts; Cascais Impact Model workshop with Portuguese Domino cards/Nov. 2024

2.2.3.4 PART TWO: Creating an actionable impact pathway (65 min)

Deciding on an impact pathway and pinpoint the actions (20 min)

Materials:

- City map, the domino arrangement, sticky notes, markers.

Activity:

Now that you have a network of impact links laid out in front of you (the domino arrangement), we are going to think about making these impacts happen. Each chain of cards (at least 3) linked with blue and/or red half circles is called an IMPACT PATHWAY. Imagine, you have a two-year timeframe.

- Decide on an impact pathway as a group and list the required actions. (20 min)

Creating an agenda: discuss stakeholders, data, finance, and regulations (25 min)

Materials:

- City map, the Impact pathway, the Impact Model wheel, sticky notes, and markers.

Activity:

With the list of actions ready, you can create a more detailed agenda. Find answers to the following questions: (25 min)

- What stakeholders need to be involved?
- What kind of data would you need to support your decisions or monitor the progress?
- What kind of financial resources do you have or would you need?
- Are there any specific tools helping or preventing the impacts from happening?

- You may locate the cards of your Impact pathway around the Impact Model wheel to understand its scope in a 360-degree visual. (The use of the Impact Model wheel is not obligatory).

Inter-group reflection & feedback collection (15+5 min)

- Briefly share your findings with other groups (each group gets 3-5 min)
- Answer a few questions on the screen (5 min)

Figure: Creating an actionable impact pathway; Bruges Impact Model workshop with Flemish Domino cards/April 2024

2.3 Prototype Impact Model workshop with the Re-Value consortium (Ålesund, 20 March 2024)

2.3.1 Objectives of the session

During the consortium meeting and city visit in Ålesund in March 2024, we tested a prototype of the gamified Impact Model workshop with the consortium, before implementing it in the Re-Value cities. The purpose of these workshops was to equip the cities and other WPs with a new entry point (a simple gamified tool) to the Impact Model and its primary functions:

- Foster co-benefits and address potential conflicts within a transformation area
- Add value to the story of the cities and their waterfront pilots
- Anchor the Impact Model for story-telling, understanding the blind spots and needs among Re-Value cities and (hopefully) later between cities and their partners
- Stimulate deep discussion on co-benefits and conflicts of interests

2.3.2 Results of the session

Participants were divided into groups of 3 or 4 and had two main interactive exercises. First, they were asked to identify the existing and potential impacts of the ongoing projects in their cities by selecting 10-14 cards out of the 46 Impact Model domino cards they each received (5-7 for current and the same number for future impacts). Using the selected cards, they each then narrated the stories of their cities to other participants around the table. Some interesting stories can be found below:

Once vibrant and green, **Rijeka**'s rivers are now overshadowed by industrial buildings and inaccessible. Citizens, deeply attached to their city's history, aim to regenerate these areas, fostering innovation and creativity. We plan to support community initiatives, particularly for youth, and combat air pollution with parks and green roofs. By enhancing public transport and pedestrian pathways, sharing energy, and reducing CO₂ emissions, they hope to create a sustainable and livable city, nurturing social innovation and a vibrant night economy.

Constanța has been focusing on reducing CO₂ emissions and improving air quality by refurbishing public buildings, boosting renewable energy, and enhancing public transport with 40 new electric buses, and bike/bus lanes. The city celebrates its cultural diversity and hosts various public events. Still, many historic buildings need investment to improve their condition. To retain young people, Constanta aims to enhance institutional capital and participation. Efforts are underway to diversify seashore services, improve traffic safety with 340 surveillance cameras, promote circularity, manage summer waste, and embrace digitalization to create a resilient, self-sufficient city.

Burgas prioritises innovation and effective use of common spaces, supported by the Smart Burgas platform, which provides crucial data on social services and transport. The city focuses on energy efficiency with a solar feasibility study and addresses climate challenges like urban heat islands and flooding by monitoring water levels. Despite poor drinking water quality, Burgas boasts over nine protected areas rich in biodiversity, aiming to integrate these into the local green economy. Efforts include enhancing green-blue functions, fostering cultural values, and promoting sustainable tourism to strengthen the city's identity and artistic influence.

Figure: The NEB Impact Model session during the Ålesund consortium meeting, March 2024

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In the second exercise, participants played the Impact Model Dominoes identifying the links between the topics they used to tell the story of their cities. They were instructed to connect the cards with blue half-circles if they recognized a co-benefit and red half-circles if the link represented a clash of interests. Some groups concentrated on a more general context and some focused on one or multiple cities. They also were very creative and came up with new interpretations of the cards and how they could be linked. At the end of this part, we had an intergroup reflection. Below, you will find one of the fascinating discussions:

In **Bruges**, the focus is on CO₂ reduction and promoting renewable energy. The city's narrow streets and limited underground space present a challenge for installing district heating from renewable sources and an efficient sewage system. Nature-based solutions could be the key to mitigating these issues. The group identified a constraint regarding the link between CO₂ reduction and digitalization bringing attention to the residual heat of data centres (they introduced a new interpretation to the “digitalization” card). Promoting active and public transport supports CO₂ reduction and enhances green-blue functions, which align with preserving Bruges's history and heritage. However, sustainable tourism remains a significant challenge, though resolving it could benefit the local green economy and employment. The group also reinterpreted the meaning of “total societal cost of ownership” believing that if you feel more “identity and belonging” toward a place, you are more invested and engaged in your community and therefore more likely to care for and be part of it. This can lead to the co-creation of things and governance or vice versa (good governance leading to more engagement/investment).

Figure: Finding co-benefits and clashes of interests using Impact Model Dominoes concentrated on the case of Bruges.

3 Impact Model workshops in the Re-Value cities

Using the method outlined in Chapter 2, Re-Value cities collaborated with NTNU to organize six on-site Impact Model workshops between March and June 2024. These workshops were conducted in all the Leading Cities (Ålesund, Bruges, Burgas, and Rimini) and two of the Replication Cities (Rijeka and Constanța). At the time of this report's submission, workshops in the remaining Replication Cities (Cascais, İzmir, and Písek) are in progress. The sections that follow provide insights into the preparation process behind these workshops, the key findings, how the outcomes are being applied to develop the cities' roadmaps, and the next steps in the project.

3.1 Ålesund Impact Model workshop (22 March 2024)

3.1.1 Workshop Context

The workshop in Ålesund was the first one in the series, and different from the format implemented in the other cities. The city invested considerable effort into designing a tailored module that would best address the specific needs and challenges it faced at the time, ensuring it aligned with the local context and goals. In the sections below, we give an overview of the participant types as well as a summary of the discussions.

3.1.2 Implementation

The workshop included **11 participants** from Ålesund municipality (different units including people that are not actively involved in Re-Value), Junior Achievement (Ungt Entreprenørskap), and Sørsida Utvikling AS, and NTNU. The participants represented all 5 pillars of the Impact Model. No politicians were present. Held at the **Hotel Brosundet**, the discussions were held in **1 focus group**.

Figure: Ålesund Impact Model workshop, participants' background (N=11)

The municipality uses several methods for sustainability (e.g. U4SSC United for Smart Sustainable Cities), and the Impact Model can provide an extension of these, adapted to the local context. These insights and experiences were used to brainstorm on concrete suggestions, such as:

- People walking or biking could earn a discount on theatre tickets
- Can the energy generated by the cruise ship propellers be used as renewable energy?
- Can we frame the discussion around “smart” parking rather than using the words “removing parking”?

After a round of concrete suggestions, we took a step back and discussed the broader picture. Can we distinguish better between what we can do right now, what we can do next year, further ahead in time?

For example, Ålesund is built for cars - how do we remedy that with urban planning and design and not just incentivising people with theatre tickets? Can we use youth entrepreneur programmes and companies to a bigger extent to develop new ideas that generate co-benefits in terms of greenhouse gas emissions and quality of urban space, and really challenge the status quo? Can they also help deal with (apparent) conflicts of interest?

3.1.3 Reflections and learnings

There were some important learnings in preparing the Impact Model Workshop in Ålesund:

- Language is important: the terminology should not be too academic (very few participants will know what “LCA” is for example), and the workshop and materials should ideally be done in the local planning. This will allow the participants to express themselves freely when discussing complex topics such as municipal planning.
- The selection of stakeholder is important, and this is also connected with the stage of the project/process that participants discuss. The current version of the Impact model/framework does not handle these two aspects.
- The introduction of the project and facilitation is important and must be adapted to the local context and will vary with the timeline and state of the project.

The facilitators/project team agreed that it would be great to be able to adapt the Impact Model and explore and update its elements for local use. This is in fact something that also other cities (in other projects) have requested; such opportunities will be included in the next steps of the Impact Model development and implementation.

3.2 Bruges (15-16 April 2024)

3.2.1 Workshop Information Card

Preparation	3 online meetings and 1 in-person in Brussels during the New European Bauhaus festival (the first meeting was held on Jan. 31st)
Format	Lunch to lunch (an afternoon session followed by a morning session)
Date	15-16 April
Session 1 (Workshop)	April 15 (13:30-17:30): Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders
Session 2 (Reflection)	April 16 (09:00-12:30): Bruges Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting
Targeted site	Quay District (Kaaidistrict)
Sessions' leader	Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU)
Group facilitators in session 1	Lies Debbaut & Koen Timmerman (Bruges Municipality) Annemie Wyckmans & Han Vandevyvere (NTNU)
Workshop's language	Mainly Flemish in both sessions (only the instructions were given in English)
Dominoes' language	Flemish (the local team did the translation and printing)

3.2.2 Implementation

3.2.2.1 Session 1: Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders

Figure: Stakeholders in Bruges working with the Impact model Dominoes

On the day of the workshop, **4 discussion groups** were organised, each focused on a specific area: 1) Overall Quay District, 2) Retail cluster, 3) Maker’s district, and 4) Food hub. These group configurations were agreed upon during the preparation phase, and participants were invited accordingly. A balanced mix of internal and external stakeholders attended, representing diverse disciplines, with **39 participants** in total. Held at the **Kaaidistrict police station**, the workshop proceeded smoothly with participants pre-assigned to groups of **7-10 members**. Figures below demonstrate the workshop participants’ backgrounds and discussion groups’ diverse mix of members.

Figure: Bruges Impact Model workshop, participants’ background (N=39)

Figure: Bruges Impact Model workshop, the mix of the discussion groups

3.2.2.2 Session 2: Bruges Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting

The second session was held at the Bruges municipality in which 11 representatives from the Bruges Re-Value core group, 2 experts from NTNU and 1 from VITO participated. 2 colleagues from VITO also joined the session as observers. In total, 16 people were present. Taking the output of the stakeholder workshop and intersecting it with the Kaaidistrict's unfinalised action plan, we dove deeper into making the discussions more concrete for the action plan in an intensive and super active 3.5-hour workshop.

What follows briefly captures the exciting results of the two sessions:

Figure: The Re-Value Bruges core group having a workshop together with NTNU

3.2.3 Reflections and Learnings (session 1)

3.2.3.1 Visual Representation of Group Discussion Outcomes

Map of the site: Kaaidistrict

Group 1: Overall Kaaidistrict

Group 2: Maker's district

Group 3: Retail Cluster

Group 4: Food Hub

3.2.3.2 Key Themes and Insights

Liveliness in the Kaaidistrict:

- Liveliness was identified as a significant value for Kaaidistrict that could enhance the sense of identity and belonging to the area. It was also noted that Kaaidistrict can become more lively if it promotes accessibility of services and mixed-use. There is a need for new governance models focused on sustainability, inclusiveness, and diversity.
- Circularity regarding water flows, energy flows, resources, food, ... should be central to upgrading the area.
- Kaaidistrict should be regenerated in a way that integrates it in the existing context. However, it should not become TOO nice (“braaf” in Flemish).
- Participants agreed that strengthening the green and blue networks in the area is crucial for fostering “liveliness.” Although existing infrastructure may pose challenges, these should not hinder efforts to expand these networks and improve connections between neighbourhoods.
- Greater emphasis should be placed on integrating water as a central and inseparable element of the community in the Kaaidistrict.
- Using the bike lanes connecting the “UNESCO egg” with the beaches along the coast could provide opportunities for the promotion of sustainable tourism in the Kaaidistrict.
- The risks of noise/air pollution associated with freight traffic should be taken into account.
- Kaaidistrict is situated next to the inner port. Therefore, the link to the harbor should not be ignored. New retail and housing will have to be developed and exist harmoniously with the harbor.

Principles for Meaningful and Sustainable Change:

- Solution-based co-creative thinking
- Addressing the financial framework
- Improving contract management
- Fostering interwoven functions
- Prioritising climate neutrality
- Promoting socially relevant entrepreneurship

Clear Program, Accountable Coordinator, Co-Creation, and Societal Networks:

- Participants recognized that, in the process of transforming the water pilot, governance models may need to take precedence over spatial aspects. This underscores the importance of concrete mandates and a clear program. In this context, the City Atelier should serve as the central actor, with accountability playing a crucial role in ensuring success.
- The transformation and its clear processes should help create robust societal networks.

Growth and Going Fossil-Free, Opportunities and Connections:

- How should we address companies reliant on the water? One approach could be relocating less-polluting companies closer to the Maker’s District, while placing those that generate higher levels of pollution (of any kind) farther away.

- We need to identify opportunities by determining which concessions are currently available and which will become available in the near future. While the harbor is developing its vision, the municipality has not been closely connected to this process.
- Benefiting from the opportunity of taking energy/heat of the water: aquathermal installations. It's one of the identified sustainable heat sources which should be used to heat all buildings and dwellings fossil-free.

3.2.3.3 Agendas for Actionable Impact Pathways

Short-term:

- Designing communal green spaces in the Kaaidistrict.
- Making children's zones integrated with the needs of inhabitants.

Medium to Long-term:

- Creating a dialogue with the harbor understanding what they want and what is possible. We need well-defined contracts that foster constructive discussions about the future, moving beyond the current "this is not possible" mindset—or the lack of dialogue altogether. The harbor should also recognize the benefits of a thriving district nearby, including increased workforce availability, improved accessibility, enhanced facilities, more attractive spaces, and greater operational efficiency.
- Creating a logistics axis in the middle of the site, between existing commercial buildings, helping reduce the impact of freight traffic on the surrounding environment, benefiting residential areas and shoppers.
- Consolidating fragmented parking spaces and reducing the number of entry and exit points, making access by bicycle safer and more appealing.
- Developing new business models and spatial regeneration models that allow us to use the space better.
- Striking a balance between enhancing green spaces and generating renewable energy on the site.
- Preserving and strengthening heritage connections, such as the 1930s dwellings linked to the site's former ceramics and brickworks.
- It would be beneficial to make a special vehicle between the city and the harbour that helps develop the area ("stads- en havenontwikkelingsbedrijf" in Flemish similar to Sørsida Utvikling AS in Ålesund). The city can take on the role of facilitator, bringing together various stakeholders to develop a unified and integrated vision. To support this process, a clear mandate must be established, potentially funded by the harbor fund.

3.2.3.4 Feedback on the Workshop Format

Participants valued the engaging discussions with diverse stakeholders, which fostered new insights and connections, as well as the fruitful co-creation and potential partnerships. They praised the respectful interactions, the innovative Domino system, the encouragement of creative thinking, and the use of interactive, accessible, and visually appealing tools like cards and maps.

Challenges:

During the workshop, some participants were sceptical/confused about:

- Discussions lacked depth and clarity, making it difficult to reach conclusions or identify concrete actions.
- The connection between the concept study and the decided policy was unclear, as were the sequences of actions to be taken.
- Uncertainty about how the insights would be documented and integrated into the action plan.
- The complexity!

Lessons Learned:

- Some of the confusions could have been avoided if more explanation was provided about the Impact Model, its principles and its application in the beginning of the workshop.
- Participants could have been engaged if the bigger picture of the project and the sequences had been made more clear.

3.2.4 Reflections and Learnings (session 2)

The session lasted for a little over 3.5 hours. It started with short summaries about the stakeholder workshop on the previous day by each facilitator. Next, we combined the results of the workshop with the action plan items in an active workshop style (see picture below). After a couple of rounds of reflection, participants clustered the action items and did a 30-minute hackathon to draft actionable agendas for the clustered action items. The following is a summary of the actionable agendas participants developed for the four main action item clusters:

3.2.4.1 Workshop Contribution to Bruges' Roadmap

Energy Action Cluster:

It was agreed to start with more accessible options, such as installing modular entrance boxes, while acknowledging that alternatives like solar panels, green roofs, water retention systems, and roof tiles require further study. Developers will also explore aquathermal and geothermal solutions, and the potential for generating energy from the port was discussed. It is crucial for the city to develop a comprehensive energy plan to maintain better control over future developments. The time frame, data, or financing were not discussed in the given time. Key stakeholders identified include all inhabitants and several partners e.g., the non-profit organisation "Bruges Gives Energy." The legal aspects of "energy sharing" need to be explored, as it remains complex, and the "Re-Value study budget" could be allocated to this effort. As for KPIs, it was proposed to measure renewable energy generation, the number of families supplied with this energy, the amount of unused space available, fossil fuel consumption reduction, and the percentage increase in renewable energy use.

Kaai Pavilion:

The group proposed using the gas station site to create a pavilion based on a maximum circular approach, developing a preliminary concept to discuss with stakeholders and architects. The pavilion could collaborate

with local stakeholders on "spaces of possibility" from 2025 to 2027, leading up to the next Triennale. The project is planned for realisation in 2025, with financing available from the "Circular Hub," "Re-Value," "Recovery Story," and "Pavilions Available: Belgique." The methodology will follow a cooperative approach, with key stakeholders including the Circular Hub, architecture students, colleagues, and social partners. Data and regulations were not discussed. Two KPIs were identified: the amount of circular material used and the number of visitors to the pavilion.

Mobility Action Cluster:

Several key actions were identified, including rearranging exits on the R30, creating dedicated bicycle parking spaces, developing parking areas with maximum capacity standards, utilising adaptive structures for parking buildings to allow for future repurposing, and rethinking and managing trade agreements. While the timeframe, data, financing, stakeholders, and regulations were not discussed, KPIs will focus on monitoring the modal shift and the number of signed covenants.

Fostering a Green/Blue Network with Legal Framework Action Cluster:

The identified actions include establishing a quality chamber and reviewing softening measures. The timeframe will be determined based on the spatial execution plan ("ruimtelijk uitvoeringsplan" or in short RUP) and regulatory burdens. Financing can be obtained from the "Re-Value," port city fund, and urban renewal projects. Key stakeholders include inhabitants and the port (government). Data will be sourced from GIS and IT systems. Tools will involve expertise in the quality chamber, high-quality architecture, and urban development companies with mandates. Regulations will be governed by cooperation agreements. KPIs will focus on the number of RUPs, developed regulations, and environmental permits that cannot be challenged.

3.2.4.2 Cross-Re-Value Insights

- In Rimini, the municipality has successfully acted as a facilitator, coordinating efforts among various stakeholders. Sharing this experience could provide valuable insights for Bruges.
- The Sørsida Utvikling AS in Ålesund could be a good example and worth replication in Bruges as a special vehicle between the city and the harbour.

3.2.5 Next Steps

- Leveraging WP1 processes—Impact Model, story building, scenario building, and investment/partnership building—to experiment with outcomes and re-evaluate urban planning and design in the Kaaidistrict integrating the harbour.
- Revising Kaaidistrict's action plan based on the results of the workshop and taking it to the aldermen for further discussion/confirmation (already done at the submission time of this report).
- Establishing a Kaai studio for implementing the action plan.
- Communicating the workshop output to the participants and using the method of the workshop to create and sustain engagement with the locals (e.g., holding similar Impact Model workshops).

3.3 Rijeka (25 April 2024)

3.3.1 Workshop Information Card

Preparation	1 in-person meeting in Amsterdam during the CrAft Consortium event followed by 2 online meetings (first talk on Feb. 28th)
Format	One full day (morning and afternoon sessions)
Date	25 April
Session 1 (Workshop)	April 25 (09:00-12:20): Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders
Session 2 (Reflection)	April 25 (14:00-16:30): Rijeka Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting
Targeted site	ExportDrvo building
Sessions' leader	Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU)
Group facilitators in session 1	Annemie Wyckmans, Marjan Khaleghi, and Katherine Weir (NTNU)
Workshop's language	Mainly English with some Croatian (session 1), English (session 2)
Dominoes' language	English

3.3.2 Implementation

3.3.2.1 Session 1: Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders

Figure: Stakeholders in Rijeka working with the Impact Model Dominoes

In Rijeka, we did not take the whole waterfront pilot as the topic of the workshop; the discussions were centred around one massive industrial heritage building called “ExportDrvo”. Participants were pre-assigned to **3 discussion groups** in a way that the maximum background diversity could be met. Held at **RiHub**, a coworking space close to "ExportDrvo," the workshop brought together **22 participants**. Each group comprised **7-8 members**, including a facilitator. The following Figures highlight the participants' backgrounds and the diversity within the groups.

Figure: Rijeka Impact Model workshop, participants' background (N=22)

Figure: Rijeka Impact Model workshop, the mix of the discussion groups

3.3.2.2 Session 2: Rijeka Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting

The second session took place in the afternoon at the same venue as the morning workshop. It was attended by seven participants: 3 representatives from the city of Rijeka, 1 partner from the University of Nova Gorica, and 3 NTNU representatives. Since Rijeka's second Innovation Camp had been held the day before, this session focused on further discussing the findings from both the workshop and the Innovation Camp.

What follows briefly captures the main outputs of these two sessions:

Figure: The Re-Value Rijeka core group having a meeting together with NTNU

3.3.3.2 Key Themes and Insights

National Port, Regulations, and Limitations/Opportunities:

- Rijeka is a port/industrial city and the Port of Rijeka is owned and under the jurisdiction of national authorities. Therefore, if something is planned to be implemented at the port, it should happen within the national legal framework.
- By law, a public authority can award a concession, but it must be to a company, such as Rijeka Sport (potentially linked to Sørsida Utvikling AS). The tender is scheduled to open in early 2025.

Space Use, Governance, Privatization, Affordability & Inclusivity, and Culture:

- ExportDrvo is centrally located with a connection to the waterfront, but its significance is not well defined (please see the map in section 3.3.3.1)
- As a private agency owned by the municipality, Rijeka Sport works on redesigning the building with a new business model (charging event organizers and people for the use of space). Some participants expressed concerns that this could leave the non-profit sector without a dedicated space in Rijeka. One participant remarked, "If we kill the only space, there will be no cultural economy."
- Activating business models and engaging the private sector could be crucial for ensuring long-term activities and impacts. However, privatizing public spaces may not be the ideal solution as it may also lead to gentrification.
- At the same time, fostering an "entrepreneurial culture" was suggested as a future direction for the building, given Rijeka's status as the European Capital of Culture in 2020 and the subsequent decline in artistic education.
- Politics are constantly changing, and long-term dialogues may fall apart as a result. There must be strategic policies in place that remain stable despite shifts in political direction. Only then, we can move forward with discussing business models for the use of this space.
- Culture may not be directly profitable, but that doesn't mean it can't be combined with profitable sectors. Currently, there are no large-scale fairs or strategic events in Rijeka. Festivals are moving out of the city, largely due to governance challenges and this needs to be changed.
- A deep discussion took place on how to define and differentiate "profit" and "non-profit" in public-private partnerships.

Industrial Heritage, Identity, Space Use, Sustainable Tourism, and Local Employment, vs. Urban Heat Island and Mobility:

- The building has served as a free space for various events centered on gastronomy, LGBTQ and other minority communities, and music. These activities have helped foster a stronger sense of connection among people.
- The events hosted at ExportDrvo have the potential to serve as a catalyst for promoting sustainable tourism. By aligning their themes and activities with sustainable practices, these events can attract visitors who are conscious of their environmental and social impact, fostering a more responsible form of tourism. Notable examples of this approach can be found in venues like "De Republiek" in Bruges and "Pakhuis de Zwijger" in Amsterdam. Additionally, this could positively impact local employment, as operating the venue will require at least 30-50 staff members.
- While the industrial port aesthetic is an integral part of Rijeka's identity, the presence of industrial and nearby brownfield sites and a lack of sufficient green spaces in these areas exacerbates urban heat islands.

- There is a lack of public space with green areas and adequate seating for relaxation. Regenerating the area could incorporate such aspects of place-making.
- Around the ExportDrvo, a significant portion of the space is dedicated to private cars and parking, with no specific access for pedestrians or cyclists. This needs significant improvement.

Utilization of the Building for Events:

- The space is empty; hence, all the equipment needs to be rented to make it work.
- The space is not acoustically optimized for various event types, as it was originally designed for storage rather than hosting gatherings. As a result, the indoor and outdoor noise levels were negatively associated with the building.

3.3.3.3 Agendas for Actionable Impact Pathways

Short to Medium-term:

- Defining the rules for using "ExportDrvo" and a legal framework as support for a well-functioning space
- Promoting multifunctionality
- Adapting business models to the scale and context of Rijeka
- Clear guidance for the future management of the space is needed. Small, not-for-profit, and commercial entities can work together within a single model, but with varying price levels and payment options based on their ability and willingness to pay.
- Ensuring affordability while aligning with the governance and needs of Rijeka's residents

3.3.3.4 Feedback on the Workshop Format

The workshop's innovative and gamified approach was highly appreciated by the participants, who were enthusiastic about using such tools for the first time. They expressed regret that the session lasted less than four hours and wished for double the time. Given that the city of Rijeka already incorporated the stakeholders' input to revise the space use plan (we were informed in September 2024), it is recommended to organize additional workshops involving a broader group of stakeholders to address various urban challenges and ensure inclusive decision-making. Public/community consultation is necessary to identify the needs for the space use and its management.

Challenges:

- When participants discuss sensitive topics, it becomes challenging to redirect the conversation and prevent a few individuals from dominating it, leading to repetitive discussions. While this may sometimes encourage deeper conversations, it can also make participants with less experience on the topic feel excluded.
- Managing group dynamics when two parties with conflicting interests use the discussion as an opportunity to criticize each other.
- Some of the cards were difficult to comprehend.

Lessons Learned:

- The facilitator should encourage flexibility in the discussion topics and create new cards tailored to the ongoing conversation. The flow of the dialogue is the key priority. The Impact Model and the Dominoes are designed to support the cities and facilitate discussions, not the other way around.
- The cards and their explanations need to be simplified.

3.3.4 Reflections and learnings (session 2)

We started with a recap of the Innovation Camp held the day before the Impact Model workshop, where ideas like creating new meeting places, introducing water taxis, and making beaches more popular were discussed. However, the local team felt these ideas lacked concreteness, sustainability, and economic feasibility. We then built on the workshop findings, exploring how the mindset could shift from "we could never..." to "what if...," turning utopian ideas into reality.

3.3.4.1 Workshop Contribution to Rijeka's Roadmap

A Waterfront City Culture, Taxi Boats, Energy Efficient Mobility, and Limiting Car Access:

The city center has many parking lots and unused boats. Strengthening Rijeka's connection to the water by using energy-efficient boats as a transport alternative to cars could enhance its identity as a waterfront city. While not all parking lots can be closed immediately, a gradual shift from private cars to alternative mobility options could be implemented, following the successful example of Ljubljana. Rijeka has experience transforming car-dependent routes into pedestrianized paths, which initially faced resistance but later became local favorites. The city has a Citizen Council and a participatory budget game that could be leveraged in these processes.

The local team proposed creating a movie to showcase these transformations, highlighting changes that have become part of everyday life. The video could feature a timeline with insights from big data (An amazing video was created and shown during the Rijeka city visit in late October 2024.)

Industrial Waterfront Transformation, Idea Competition, and the Lively Channel (formerly known as the Dead Channel):

We discussed the future vision for Rijeka, beyond just ExportDrvo. Many areas along the waterfront will transform over the next 25 years, and an "idea competition" for these areas would provide valuable insights. The revitalization of the Dead Channel and the creation of meeting spaces around it were also discussed.

3.3.4.2 Cross-Re-Value Insights

- Drawing inspiration from successful cases of sustainable tourism such as "De Republiek" in Bruges for ExportDrvo.
- Looking into the experience of Ålesund with "Sørsida Utvikling AS" for area transformation.

3.3.5 Next Steps

- Leveraging WP1 processes—Impact Model, story building, scenario building, and investment/partnership building—to experiment with outcomes and re-evaluate urban planning and design in Rijeka’s water pilot.
- Communicating the workshop output to the participants and using the workshop method to create and sustain engagement with the locals (e.g., holding similar Impact Model workshops for other stakeholders, students, and so forth).
- A local version of the cookbook for ExportDrvo, detailing the process of various actions, could be an interesting idea.

Figure: The Re-Value Rijeka team created posters of the two Innovation Camp ideas and displayed them during the Rijeka city visit in October 2024.

3.4 Rimini (23-24 May 2024)

3.4.1 Workshop Information Card

Preparation	2 online meetings (first talk on April 19th) and several follow-ups via email
Format	Lunch to lunch (an afternoon session followed by a morning session)
Date	23-24 May
Session 1 (Workshop)	April 23 (17:30-19:00): Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders
Session 2 (Reflection)	April 24 (09:00-12:00): Rimini Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting
Targeted site	San Giuliano waterfront pilot
Sessions' leader	Deborah Navarra (NTNU) in session 1 Alberto Della Valle (Rimini Municipality) in session 2
Group facilitators in session 1	Alberto Della Valle and Alessandra Pesaresi (Rimini Municipality) Konstantina Douka (UNIBO) Deborah Navarra and Francesco Camilli (NTNU)
Workshop's language	Italian (both sessions)
Dominoes' language	Italian (local team/NTNU did the translation & NTNU did the printing.)

3.4.2 Implementation

3.4.2.1 Session 1: Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders

Figure: Stakeholders in Rimini working with the Impact Model Dominoes

In Rimini, the specific focus of the workshop was on the San Giuliano water pilot. The pilot project concentrates on a) protecting sea ingress, b) de-seasonalisation, c) increasing attractiveness, and d) upgrading sports areas. Other related topics were identified as improving the liveability of the district and its connectivity to the city and upgrading Briolini Park. Several stakeholders of San Giuliano were invited to the workshop and were assigned to **4 discussion groups**. Held at **Laboratorio Aperto**, the workshop brought together **31 participants and 3 observers (NTNU)** with **6-8 members per group**, including a facilitator. The following two figures highlight the participants' backgrounds and the diversity of expertise within each group.

Figure: Rimini Impact Model workshop, participants' background (N=34)

Figure: Rimini Impact Model workshop, discussion groups' mix

3.4.2.2 Session 2: Rimini Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting

The next morning after the workshop, we convened again with the representatives of various offices and departments of the Rimini municipality and UNIBO representatives at the same venue. 28 people attended this meeting (27 in person and 1 online). The session began by listening to the summaries of group discussions from the previous day by each facilitator. Next, UNIBO colleagues presented their approach to using the Impact Model for a quantitative evaluation of the San Giuliano water pilot. We then sat together in an oval-shaped setting and delved deeper into the site using all the gathered insights.

What follows gives an overview of the findings in each of these two sessions:

Figure: The Re-Value Rimini core group having a meeting together with NTNU

3.4.3 Reflections and Learnings (session 1)

3.4.3.1 Visual Representation of Group Discussion Outcomes

Map of the site: San Giuliano water pilot

Group 1

Group 2

Group 3

Group 4

3.4.3.2 Key Themes and Insights

Connectivity:

- The importance of connection—both physical and non-physical—and its impact on local businesses was highlighted as a key issue.
- The lack of bridges was mentioned as a barrier for pedestrians and cyclists to navigate the site.
- Beach accessibility emerged as another key issue. Participants noted that the beach is not easily accessible to visitors, as it is reserved during the summer by local non-residents. In this context, national and regional challenges, such as "Riforma Balneari/Concessioni," were brought up.
- It appeared that San Giuliano was not well connected to other parts of the city, particularly the opposite side of the port canal and the southern seaside area. This could be traced back to the irregular ferry schedule and insufficient public transport options in terms of frequency and timetables.
- Discussions also revolved around the synergy of “connectivity” with the “quality of public space”.

Sustainable Tourism:

- Sustainable tourism was identified as a hot topic, focusing on the area’s potential to highlight identity and strengthen the community. The topic is connected to all the pillars of the Impact Model. Many unique spots could host events and bring new energy to the area. However, many operators seem discouraged, possibly due to growing residential development, and are disheartened to pursue this direction. While some people are active and generous in their efforts, there is a clear lack of wider collaboration to support sustainable tourism initiatives.

Blue/Green Infrastructure:

- While environmental protection against marine water ingress is crucial for the vitality of the water pilot, it may not have been prioritised by some participants.
- Connection is an important topic when we are concerned with blue/green infrastructure.
- Collaboration is essential for the implementation of the Nature-Based Solutions (NBS).

Investment Attractiveness:

- Due to the limited economic activity in comparison to the rest of the city, few entrepreneurs are involved in local associations or willing to contribute financially to the revitalization of San Giuliano.

Cooperation and Inclusion:

- Governance is crucial for fostering cooperation and inclusion. Listening to and observing from the ground up could serve as a foundation for a more inclusive participation process in future developments.

3.4.3.3 Agendas for Actionable Impact Pathways

Short-term:

- Adding more lighting to the beach for better visibility in the evening and at night.

- Expanding commercial services, creating attractive spots, and introducing cultural activities to benefit both tourists and residents.
- Testing and prototyping should precede costly and permanent solutions. Building temporary pedestrian bridges or organising seasonal events were suggested in this regard which could also generate the demand for connectivity. Securing financial resources and involving local residents and entrepreneurs in these activities could help ensure their success, drawing lessons from previous unsuccessful attempts.

Long-term:

- Reliable and frequent ferry connections across Porto Canale and the Marecchia River, the two primary water bodies bordering the area to the east and west, were proposed. However, nature conservation laws and lack of economic sustainability could pose barriers to implementing these solutions. The long-term vision and political will in implementing it would be paramount in this regard.
- Utilising the temporary and immaterial interventions to create appeal and establish the need for connecting implemented strategies to both intermediate and long-term goals.

3.4.3.4 Feedback on the Workshop Format

Challenges:

- In the first part of the workshop, where participants identified impacts and connections, there was a strong sense of optimism and idealistic energy. However, in the second part, when the discussion shifted to what could be achieved within a year, the focus moved away from actions and centred on problems.
- Bringing together individuals from the private and public sectors was a challenge that required specialised facilitation skills.
- Participants may get stuck if the cards or their definitions do not reflect their perspective.
- One participant, claiming a 90-year family history of hotel ownership, tended to dominate the discussion, placing all the responsibility on public authorities, particularly the municipality.

Lessons Learned:

- There is a need to involve more sectors of society, using diverse tools, approaches, and perspectives, as the issues are varied and complex. Incorporating a wider range of expertise is essential.
- The facilitator plays a crucial role in encouraging participants to think creatively and explore unconventional ideas.

3.4.4 Reflections and learnings (session 2)

The wrap-up of the workshop findings was a deep-dive to the results of the workshop and brought a more in-depth view to the surface. As far as connections are concerned, the issues are persistent, and practical, feasible solutions (rather than bridges over a river mouth) need to be considered. Additionally, the public transport service in the city remains underused, and it makes sense to improve, upgrade and promote it not

only for tourists but for the inhabitants. A potential contradiction also exists between the economic operators' desire for both a strong identity and better connectivity in the area—they seek excellent connections while also favouring a tranquil atmosphere, which may be hard to reconcile.

There is a need for greater activation of the San Giuliano community, which has diverse and evolving needs, especially as the residential population grows and outpaces the tourist component. This shift, alongside rising housing values, indicates a move towards a more residential area, raising concerns about gentrification and a potential decline in tourist offerings in favour of more housing units and professional studios.

The UNIBO presentation outlined a potential application of the Impact Model (IM), combining both quantitative and qualitative indicators. The research team emphasised that, at this stage of the project, it is the project that shapes the IM, not the other way around. They identified three scales for applying the IM: the building, the district, and the city, and categorised the indicators into two types: qualitative (assessed in an ON/OFF mode) and quantitative (parametrized). This distinction allowed for a comprehensive assessment, visualised through a radar chart that scores ON/OFF indicators with a 5 if they meet at least one criterion, while parametrized indicators receive more detailed scores. However, this representation was considered tentative, with the need for further experimentation due to potential misinterpretation in external communications. The team also recommended that designers should evaluate co-benefits as part of the process. The follow-up discussions on the UNIBO work highlighted the need to incorporate more social aspects into development plans, with a focus on balancing perceptions and objective data.

3.4.4.1 Workshop Contribution to Rimini's Roadmap

Green/Blue Infrastructure, Nature-Based Solutions, Micro-Climatic Analysis:

San Giuliano serves as a pilot area for experimenting with the green plan, which is based on NBS. The Green Plan includes participatory processes that can be oriented according to the objectives of the ATUSS, microclimatic analysis, and unique green planning for the pilot area of San Giuliano. On the other hand, the Darsena area (Rimini's Marina) is an outdated project, which is poorly integrated with the surrounding beach and negatively impacts San Giuliano. While private involvement remains challenging, it could be the key to transforming the area and driving meaningful change.

Climate Change, Tourism, Well-Being, and Connectivity:

The construction of a fish market with the provision of a multi-functional area (recreational-cultural and museum) is also on the agenda. This fish market will strengthen the cultural identity (inspired by seafaring culture) and create new attractiveness.

A city should not function as an amusement park requiring an entry ticket. Instead, tourism must be softer and more sustainable, aligned with the location's capacity, local context, and community. As we transform our community, we must prioritise climate change adaptation, mitigation, and resilience—both for the environment and the people. This raises essential questions: How can we promote these goals? What does well-being mean, and whose well-being are we addressing? We should listen closely to the local community, prioritise quality of space and life, and recognize that what benefits local residents also benefits tourists.

Place-making, Beach and River, Sports, and Attractiveness:

Lots of teenagers come to the San Giuliano beach from all over Rimini by bike. The presence of beach-volleyball courts has proved to be a powerful element of attraction for young people. The riverfront was recognised as a naturally-valuable asset of the area. These features could be further enhanced in the future.

3.4.4.2 Cross-Re-Value Insights

- Rimini has urban planning instruments (Beach Plan and the Green Plan) and urban planning strategies (ATUSS) that provide a comprehensive working ground for the conceptualization, design, and implementation of projects. Although these plans should be upgraded and revised, their existence could be a good practice for other Re-Value cities such as Burgas.
- San Giuliano tourist committee has experience in working with community business models. The mentioned committee has been engaged and empowered by participating in the project “Boroughs of the Sea Park”, conducted by the strategic plan and through participatory and voluntary initiatives for common assets management. Notably, the first civic cooperation pact was activated in the city with the BIMBY project in the garden of the “Hotel delle Nazioni”. This experience can be shared with other Re-Value cities dealing with similar topics in their waterfronts.
- The Impact Model, as a project evaluation tool across different phases, could be adopted and further refined by other Re-Value cities.

3.4.5 Next Steps

- Leveraging WP1 processes—Impact Model, story building, scenario building, and investment/partnership building—to experiment with outcomes and re-evaluate urban planning and design in the San Giuliano water pilot.
- Considering what needs to be re-valued in the legal and administrative arenas and finding ways to overcome higher-level barriers are key. This issue is present across all Re-Value cities, making it a valuable exercise to compile a list of suggestions for improving these processes, supported by the results of ongoing ground-level experiments.
- Communicating the workshop output to the participants and using the method of the workshop to create and sustain engagement with the locals (e.g., holding similar Impact Model workshops).

3.5 Burgas (11 June 2024)

3.5.1 Workshop Information Card

Preparation	1 in-person meeting in Ålesund during the Re-Value Consortium event followed by 2 online meetings (first talk on Mar. 21st)
Format	One full day (morning and afternoon sessions)
Date	11 June
Session 1 (Workshop)	June 11 (09:00-12:30): Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders
Session 2 (Reflection)	June 11 (14:00-16:00): Burgas Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting
Targeted site	Sarafovo seaside park
Sessions' leader	Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU)
Group facilitators in session 1	Yana Yancheva, Teodora Bojilcheva, and Stanimira Gospodinova (District Information Points) Zoya Stoyanova, and Gergana Ivanova (Burgas Municipality)
Workshop's language	Bulgarian with simultaneous interpretation to English (session1), English (session 2)
Dominoes' language	Bulgarian (local team did the translation & NTNU did the printing.)

3.5.2 Implementation

3.5.2.1 Session 1: Impact Model Workshop with the stakeholders

Figure: Impact Model Workshop in Burgas

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In Burgas, the specific focus of the workshop was on the Sarafovo district. Due to participation uncertainty, we could not pre-assign participants into groups. As a result, they formed **5 homogenous groups** with like-minded people or those they already knew. Held at **Sea Casino Burgas**, the workshop brought together **31 participants and 2 observers** (NTNU) with **5-7 members per group**, including a facilitator. Figures below highlight the participants' backgrounds and the diversity of expertise within each group.

Figure: Burgas Impact Model workshop, participants' background (N=33)

Figure: Burgas Impact Model workshop, discussion groups' mix

3.5.2.2 Session 2: Burgas Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting

The results of the morning session along with those of the recent Innovation Camp in Burgas were discussed in the afternoon, looking for possibilities and the path forward. This session was held in the same venue where 7 people (2 from Burgas Municipality, 2 from Sofia University, and 3 from NTNU) joined.

What follows gives an overview of the findings in each session:

Figure: Burgas Re-Value core group and NTNU reflection meeting

3.5.3 Reflections and learnings (session 1)

3.5.3.1 Visual Representation of Group Discussion Outcomes

Map of the site: Sarafovo Seaside Park

Group 1: Beach concessioners

Group 2: Architects, planners & district mayor

Group 3: Biodiversity foundation & academia

Group 4: NGOs and sea airport operators

Group 5: Bulgaria's chamber of architects

3.5.3.2 Key Themes and Insights

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) & Environmental Sustainability:

- Several groups emphasised the importance of implementing NBS. Ideas such as creating artificial islands for birdwatching, improving water drainage, and using rainwater for irrigation were central themes.
- Enhancing biodiversity, preserving natural resources, and promoting sustainable eco-mobility (bicycles, electric trains, public transport) were consistently highlighted.
- The importance of data-driven decision-making was stressed, with participants recommending further studies on the area's environmental conditions (e.g., land retreat, erosion) before implementing permanent solutions.

Shared Urban and Recreational Spaces:

- Many ideas focused on improving public spaces to foster community engagement and tourism. Suggestions included enhancing shared urban areas, creating pedestrian and cycling lanes, and integrating recreational infrastructure like adventure parks and amphitheatres.
- Cultural and historical zones were also proposed, along with improvements to archaeological sites to promote cultural tourism.

Infrastructure Development:

- Groups stressed the need for better connectivity between Sarafovo and Burgas through sustainable transport options and regulated parking.
- The area's capacity should be scaled to anticipate future increases in users and visitors. A strategic implementation plan for developing the area zone by zone and stage by stage, with pilot testing of solutions, was suggested.

Community and Stakeholder Engagement:

- The workshop revealed the importance of engaging local inhabitants and businesses alongside national and local authorities. Local stakeholders must actively participate in the planning and implementation phases to ensure long-term success.
- Regular stakeholder meetings were recommended to sustain collaboration and refine the development plan.

3.5.3.3 Agendas for Actionable Impact Pathways

Short-Term (2-4 years):

- Develop a detailed technical design project for the pilot area, incorporating insights from the workshop.
- Continue strategic planning for infrastructure improvements, focusing on eco-friendly mobility solutions.
- Encourage regular stakeholder meetings to ensure ongoing collaboration and input on evolving plans.

Medium-Term (3-5 years):

- Begin implementation of nature-based solutions, such as rainwater collection systems, cycling infrastructure, and birdwatching platforms
- Explore financing options, including national grants and European Union funding, for both infrastructure and environmental projects.

Long-Term:

- Foster community engagement through public awareness campaigns and further involvement of local businesses and residents.
- Consider the integration of cultural and recreational spaces to enhance both the local quality of life and tourism appeal.

3.4.3.4 Feedback on the Workshop Format

Challenges:

- Some groups experienced difficulties aligning with the workshop's objectives or managing time effectively.
- There was a need for clearer communication of terminology and workshop goals, especially in the beginning, to ensure full understanding among participants.
- Coordinating the collaboration of institutions and stakeholders with varying expertise was challenging.

Lessons Learned:

- Gamification tools, such as the domino game, helped engage participants and foster active discussions.
- In future workshops, participants with diverse expertise should be mixed more thoroughly to encourage cross-disciplinary insights.
- Every potential investment should be based on thorough data and analysis to ensure informed decision-making.

3.5.4 Reflections and learnings (session 2)

The local team found the workshop methods novel and quite different from their usual approach, which initially led to reluctance in engaging with the activities, especially the game. Despite efforts to mix stakeholders across tables, participants formed groups by field (e.g., beach concessioners, architects & planners, biodiversity experts), limiting cross-disciplinary interaction. This segregation influenced the discussions; for example, the beach concessioners focused on individual topics without making connections, while other groups demonstrated a broader perspective, linking various issues beyond isolated topics. During workshop planning, an additional round of stakeholder mapping ensured careful participant selection. With the participation of property owners, the first step was taken toward collaboration with community members. Upon reflecting on the workshop findings, the urgency to develop a long-term vision was recognised.

3.5.4.1 Workshop Contribution to the Burgas' Roadmap

In an attempt to identify the focal points for the long-term vision, the following topics were deemed vital:

Year-Round Beach Activities:

Local business owners expressed concerns that any type of change might threaten their seasonal income, highlighting their reliance on the three-month summer period to support their families. While valid, this perspective needs to be balanced with the severe impacts of climate change on coastal areas, urging a shift toward long-term site planning. Expanding tourism beyond summer, with diverse activities in spring and autumn, could offer solutions.

Environment and Biodiversity:

The port's construction has altered the sea ecosystem, affecting seagrass, sea temperatures, and currents, which could make the current way of using the site unfeasible within a few years. Some stakeholder groups, already aware of climate impacts like the destruction of the Bulgarian biodiversity centre by a hurricane, explored connections between Sarafovo and Burgas, focusing on biodiversity. Ideas such as creating eco-parks, and islands for bird watching, a prominent topic at the latest Innovation Camp, are being considered to enhance sustainability and conservation efforts.

Connectivity, and Parking:

Connectivity remains a critical issue, closely tied to private car use (highlighted as a cultural trait in Bulgaria) and coastal parking challenges. Participants focused heavily on parking solutions, such as an underground parking facility. Although this option can severely impact the sea and coastal ecosystem, it may be considered in the future if the site's geology report supports it. This emphasis on parking raises the question of whether stakeholders can envision broader possibilities for the area. Data collection and scenario building will be essential for exploring options beyond Digital Twins, especially with a new electric train project planned to connect the city centre to the airport soon, which could also benefit Sarafovo.

Other Potentials:

Additional ideas included using the collected rainwater as an attraction (e.g., a waterfall), and exploring the archaeological site in Sarafovo which may be under-researched at the moment.

The city engages citizen groups in discussions on various topics and maintains a strategic development plan website. Core local groups could also be more actively involved in these processes. Continuous engagement and keeping people informed on how their ideas are being used remain essential.

3.5.4.2 Cross-Re-Value Insights

- Rimini's 15 years of experience in transforming its coastal park, Parco del Mare, through stakeholder coalitions could inspire similar efforts in Burgas.
- Both Burgas and Rimini creatively incorporate the sound of the sea in artistic projects (e.g., Burgas's Salty People, and Rimini's San Giuliano concert).
- Burgas and Izmir share significant bird ecosystems, including flamingos, emphasising nature conservation.

- Another concept from the Innovation Camp in Burgas is utilising sheep’s wool for insulation in eco-houses, which may also be of interest for sustainable building in Ålesund.
- While experimenting with short-term solutions is valuable, it’s essential to consider long-term viability and sustained engagement. We can look into the recent “Journey to Change” session in Brussels during which many relevant ideas emerged.

3.5.5 Next Steps

- Leveraging WP1 processes—Impact Model, story building, scenario building, and investment/partnership building—to experiment with outcomes and re-evaluate urban planning and design in the Sarafovo district.
- Making a stage-by-stage action plan (a living document) based on the workshop results and other ongoing processes.
- Rethinking the stakeholders who should be involved in the consultation and implementation of the action plan.
- Communicating the workshop output to the participants and scheduling follow-up sessions or even other impact model workshops.
- Communicating the design concept of the pilot area with the local community and interested stakeholders and developing an effective communication strategy and campaign to update on the progress of the design concept at regular stakeholders’ workshops and events.

3.6 Constanța (20 June 2024)

3.6.1 Workshop Information Card

Preparation	1 online meeting and several follow-ups via WhatsApp (first talk on May 23)
Format	One full day (morning and afternoon sessions)
Date	20 June
Session 1 (Workshop)	June 20 (09:00-12:30): Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders
Session 2 (Reflection)	June 20 (15:00-15:30): Constanța Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting
Targeted site	The whole waterfront pilot (the peninsula with 4 identified zones)
Sessions' leader	Marjan Khaleghi (NTNU)
Group facilitators in session 1	George Lupascu, Irina Elena Crista, and Adrian Vladu (Zone Metropolitan Constanța and Constanța Municipality) Annemie Wyckmans, Marjan Khaleghi, and Katherine Weir (NTNU)
Workshop's language	Romanian and English (session 1), English (session 2)
Dominoes' language	Romanian (local team did the translation & NTNU did the printing.)

3.6.2 Implementation

3.6.2.1 Session 1: Impact Model Workshop with the Stakeholders

Figure: Stakeholders doing Impact Model Workshop in Constanța

In Constanța, the focus of the workshop was on the whole waterfront pilot. The local team pre-assigned the participants into **3 discussion groups**. Held at a hall inside **Constanța Municipal Council**, the workshop brought together **21 participants** with **5-9 members per group**, including a facilitator from the local team and a supporter from NTNU. The two figures below highlight the participants' backgrounds and the diversity of expertise within each group.

Figure: Constanța Impact Model workshop, participants' background (N=22)

Figure: Constanța Impact Model workshop, discussion groups' mix

3.6.2.2 Session 2: Constanța Re-Value Core Group and NTNU Meeting

In the afternoon, we reflected on the discussions during the Impact Model workshop and the Tactical Urbanism exercise during the study visit in Constanța that had happened right before the workshop. The two were closely interconnected and the exchange of ideas brought interesting ideas to surface. This session was held in an informal setting in open air within walking distance of the workshop venue. 9 people (6 from Constanța municipality and Zone Metropolitan Constanța, and 3 from NTNU) were present.

What follows gives an overview of the findings in each session:

Figure: The Constanța Re-Value core group and NTNU meeting

3.6.3 Reflections and Learnings (session 1)

3.6.3.1 Visual Representation of Group Discussion Outcomes

Map of the site: Peninsula with 4 identified zones

Group 1

Group 2

Group 3

3.6.3.2 Key Themes and Insights

Smart and Clean Mobility, NO CARs:

- Group 1 specifically concentrated on the idea of sustainable transport and connectivity. They proposed smart and clean mobility (e.g., having electric grids and banning all the cars) to be added inside the Peninsula area benefiting both inhabitants and visitors.
- This group also suggested linking the historical city centre to Mamaia resort through a water bus line.

Identity and Engagement through Events:

- The focus of group 2 was on sustaining the involvement of the local community through the organisation of cultural, sport and youth events.
- Such events could promote the sense of identity and the desire to preserve the area and its values.

Architectural/Cultural Special Quality, Accessibility, Green Space, and Digitalization:

- Group 3 discussed the architectural and cultural aspects of the area. The Peninsula holds a lot of historical heritage which can be leveraged as a bonding tool for people living and working in the Peninsula and the city.
- The historical part could become more friendly for people with strollers or on wheelchairs.
- The Peninsula is the heart of the city in which we would need more green space. We need to understand how inhabitants see the area and what we can do to help them love it.
- As more historical buildings are refurbished, it is important to be mindful of the risk of gentrification.
- Young people may feel disconnected from their historical heritage, which is a critical issue that needs to be addressed.

3.6.3.3 Agendas for Actionable Impact Pathways

Short-Term:

- Organising various kinds of events in the area to promote the sense of ownership and keep the community engaged.
- Encouraging residents of historical buildings to open their homes to locals and visitors, potentially by hosting community kitchens, serving breakfast to guests, or offering similar experiences. This could help prevent gentrification in the area.

Long-Term:

- Softly pushing all the cars out of the Peninsula and adding more sustainable means of transport in it. Water bus could also be considered to make the Peninsula more connected to the areas farther away.
- Protecting the cultural and historical heritage of the area by promoting different municipality programs, including the identification and absorption of different fundings opportunities for the refurbishment of the buildings.

3.6.3.4 Feedback on the Workshop Format

Lessons Learned:

- The workshop co-creation method was novel for the participants and worked very well for people to open up and put their minds together to do problem-solving.
- Some believed that more people would participate if they were informed.
- A digital workshop was proposed primarily to make it more accessible to a wider audience.

3.6.4 Reflections and learnings (session 2)

3.6.4.1 Workshop Contribution to Constanța's Roadmap

In addition to the ideas and proposed actions discussed in the learnings from Session 1, we identified two additional key topics. For further insights related to the roadmap, please refer to sections 3.6.3.2 and 3.6.3.3.

The Vision for the Peninsula is Missing:

Funding will be secured through various means, but the primary focus must remain on the overarching vision. This vision helps clarify the bigger picture and determine the priorities and timing of each step in the process. The Peninsula serves as the city's living room—a central space where people come together to celebrate, relax, and connect. To refine this concept, it's essential to incorporate the dreams, desires, and needs of the peninsula's residents.

Digitalisation and Connection:

Digitalization can be harnessed to strengthen bonds and connections, particularly with specific stakeholder groups like youth. A comprehensive communication strategy should be developed for the entire Peninsula and the city. This could include creating a dedicated micro-site within the municipality's website to serve as a communication hub. Additionally, reaching different age groups through their preferred social media platforms can help maximise the strategy's impact.

3.6.4.2 Cross-Re-Value Insights

- The case of water transport was also suggested in Rijeka. Venice could be taken as a good example for the promotion of water buses (Vaporetto in Venice).
- Gentrification could be the case in several of our waterfront cities such as Rijeka. Ideas and best practices could be experimented in these waterfront pilots.

3.6.5 Next Steps

- Leveraging WP1 processes—Impact Model, story building, scenario building, and investment/partnership building—to experiment with outcomes and re-evaluate urban planning and design in the Peninsula District.

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- Making a stage-by-stage action plan (a living document) based on the workshop results and other ongoing processes.
- More stakeholders and inhabitants should be involved in co-creation processes.
- Communicating the workshop output to the participants and scheduling follow-up sessions or replicating it with a border audience. The weekly events on Tomis Boulevards have the potential to be leveraged as a platform for discussing urban transformation topics using the story-building Innovation Cycle, art, and culture.

Figure: The weekly events on Tomis Boulevard, Constanța

4 General insights from the Impact Model workshops

Here are some of the first general conclusions across Impact Model workshops:

The general uptake is positive. Participants appreciate the way of building a whole-systems view with regard to a given project or challenge. Being tasked with identifying site qualities based on the stack of Impact Model cards, and then discussing potential co-benefits and conflicts between these, helps unearthing aspects and possibilities that workshop participants would otherwise not directly think of.

The workshops tend to gather stakeholders that would otherwise not meet and discuss together. The participants tend to perceive these joint workshops as enriching. The card games tend to pull participants out of their usual roles and perspectives, which helps to create new insights; it even supports respectful discussions between stakeholders that tend to have conflicting roles. In PART ONE, being asked to identify site qualities and discussing how these qualities can mutually reinforce each other - or where they generate potential conflicts - helps the participants to find common ground. PART TWO invites the participants to explore concrete pathways towards addressing a prioritised challenge on which they agreed in PART ONE.

Certain topics within the Impact Model, such as “total societal cost of ownership,” are consistently challenging for participants to understand, not just experts. This is largely due to each field's unique jargon and the participants' varying familiarity with technical terms from other disciplines. To address this, we view the Impact Model and Dominoes as tools that must be simplified to ensure accessibility for both experts and non-experts. Our aim is to create a shared language that everyone can understand and use effectively. While participants are encouraged to interpret and expand on topics within their expertise, the foundational language must serve as a common ground, fostering collaboration and cross-disciplinary understanding. This simplified language aims to break down barriers caused by specialized terminologies, enabling meaningful engagement among participants with diverse backgrounds. Additionally, we plan to develop an even more simplified version for younger audiences, ensuring inclusivity and extending the tool's reach to inspire the next generation.

On several occasions, participants started to stack the domino cards on the map and vertically in order to accommodate multiple and complex linking patterns. This indicates that the tool is flexible enough to accommodate complexity while maintaining its accessibility by sticking to its simple rules.

5 Conclusions and next steps

This report describes how the gamified Impact Model workshops were developed, and their first testing in the consortium and in six of the Re-Value cities. In Autumn 2024, WP1 will organise Impact Model workshops with the three remaining Re-Value cities (İzmir , Cascais and Písek).

We aim to use the findings from the Impact Model workshops to inform the cities' on-the-ground work and integrate them with the Innovation Cycles. This iterative process could make the Impact Model and Innovation Cycles framework more concrete and actionable, as they provide mutual feedback based on the cities' real experiments and practices. This integration will help update and refine the Impact Model into a dual-purpose tool: 1. To guide discussions among diverse stakeholders and 2. To further operationalize it within the cities' initiatives. Additionally, it can serve as a framework for showcasing the outcomes of re-valued processes and projects, inspiring other cities that are facing similar challenges. This approach will be implemented during the project's remaining time and reported in D1.5 Re-Value Impact Model (Final Version).

We will use the outcomes to begin discussions with the cities on how this updated model can support the implementation of their Waterfront Pilots and long-term Territorial Transformation Plans (WP2-5/6). The insights gained will also inform the design, implementation, and documentation of the cities' impact pathways in collaboration with WP7.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Abbreviations and acronyms used in the report

Abbreviation	Terms
CrAft	Creating actionable future (project)
IC	Innovation Cycle
ICLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability
IM	Impact Model
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NEB-IM	NEB Impact Model
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
UNIBO	University of Bologna
VITO	Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek
WP	Work package

About Re-Value – Re-Valuing Urban Quality & Climate Neutrality in European Waterfront Cities

The Re-Value partnership consists of nine European waterfront cities and selected European organisations that work to make the urban transition irresistible for everyone. This is done by demonstrating how climate neutrality and urban quality can be aligned, by re-valuing the cities' connection to their waterfronts, strengthening co-benefits and mitigating potential adverse impacts.

Ålesund (Norway), Bruges (Belgium), Burgas (Bulgaria), and Rimini (Italy) demonstrate how integrated urban planning and design can be optimally deployed to achieve climate neutrality and significantly reduce GHG emissions by 2030. In addition, Cascais (Portugal), Constanța (Romania), İzmir (Türkiye), Písek (Czechia), and Rijeka (Croatia) learn, replicate and develop their own participatory story-building, data-driven scenarios, and financial and partnership models on integrated urban planning and design to accelerate their journeys to climate neutrality.

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Learn more about the partnership and the outcomes on re-value-cities.eu.

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